

Comparative Analysis of Various Multipliers Based on Performance

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Abstract

In digital signal processing, computer arithmetic, and VLSI applications where speed, size, and power consumption are crucial design considerations, efficient multiplier architectures are crucial. The array multiplier, booth multiplier, Wallace tree multiplier, and dadda multiplier are the four commonly used multipliers that are compared in this study. Key performance measures like area, switching speed, latency, and power consumption were the focus of the evaluation. To evaluate each multiplier's performance under common computational circumstances, a simulation was conducted using the Xilinx ISE. By clarifying the trade-offs between various architectures, this research aids in the selection of the best multipliers for digital systems that require high performance and low power consumption.

Keywords: *Digital Multipliers, Array Multiplier, Booth Multiplier, Wallace Tree Multiplier, Low-Power Design, High-Speed Computing, VLSI Design, Hardware Optimization, FPGA Implementation, Power Dissipation, Area Efficiency, Parallel Multiplication, Arithmetic Circuits.*

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Introduction

Multiplication is a fundamental operation in digital signal processing, computer arithmetic, and VLSI design and plays a crucial role in high-performance computing applications. The multiplier efficiency significantly affects the overall performance of digital circuits, particularly in terms of power consumption, speed, and area utilization. Various multiplier architectures have been developed to optimize these parameters, each with its own advantages and tradeoffs.

Among these architectures, the Array Multiplier is known for its straightforward design, but suffers from higher power consumption and area requirements owing to extensive full-adder usage. The Booth Multiplier enhances hardware efficiency by encoding operands to reduce the number of computations; however, additional logic may introduce latency. The Wallace Tree Multiplier minimizes partial products using parallel reduction techniques, improving speed but at the cost of increased complexity and power dissipation. The Dadda Multiplier, an optimized variant of the Wallace Tree approach, further reduces the area and delay while still facing power-dissipation challenges.

Given the importance of selecting an optimal multiplier for different applications, this study provides a comparative analysis of these four architectures and evaluates key performance metrics, such as power dissipation, delay, area, and switching speed. Using the Xilinx ISE for simulation,

this research aims to offer insights into the trade-offs associated with each multiplier, aiding in the selection of the most suitable architecture for high-performance, low-power digital systems.

Multiplier and Its Types

Array Multiplier

An array multiplier is an efficient layout for a combinational multiplier. Multiplication of two binary number can be obtained with one micro-operation by using a combinational circuit that forms the product bit all at once thus making it a fast way of multiplying two numbers since only delay is the time for the signals to propagate through the gates that forms the multiplication array. In the array multiplier, consider two binary numbers, A and B, of m and n bits. There are mn summands that are produced in parallel by a set of mn AND gates. n x n multiplier requires n(n-2) full adders, n half-adders and n² AND gates. Also, in array multiplier worst case delay where is (2n+1) td. Array Multiplier gives more power consumption as well as optimum number of components required, but the delay for this multiplier is larger. It also requires larger number of gates because of which area is also increased; due to this array multiplier is less economical (Thapliyal, & Arabnia, 2007; Mano, 1993). Thus, it is a fast multiplier, but its hardware complexity is high (Stohmann, & Barke, 2022).

Booth Multiplier

Another improvement in the multiplier is a reduction in the number of partial products generated. The Booth recording multiplier is one such multiplier; it scans the three bits at a time to reduce number of partial products (Chu, 2002). These three bits are: the two bit from the present pair; and a third bit from the high-order bit of an adjacent lower order pair. After examining each triplet of bits, the triplets are converted by Booth logic into a set of five control signals used by the adder cells in the array to control the operations performed by adder cells. To speed up the multiplication Booth encoding performs several steps of multiplication at once. Booth's algorithm takes advantage of the fact that an adder subtractor is nearly as fast and is small as a simple adder. From the basics of Booth Multiplication it can be proved that the addition/subtraction operations can be skipped if the successive bits in multiplicand are the same. If 3 consecutive bits are the same, the addition/subtraction operation can be omitted. Thus in most of the cases the delay associated with Booth Multiplication is smaller than that associated with the Array Multiplier. However the performance of the Booth Multiplier for delay is input-data- dependent. In the worst case the delay with a booth multiplier on a per-array multiplier (Parate, 2008). The method of Booth recording reduces the numbers of adders and hence the delay required to produce partial sums by examining three bits simultaneously. The high performance of booth multipliers have the drawback of power consumption. The reason is large number of adder cells, which consume a large amount of power (Chu, 2002).

Wallace Tree Multiplier

A fast process for the multiplication of two numbers was developed by Robinson, & Swartzlander, 1998). Using this method, a three step process is used to multiply two numbers; the bit products are formed, the bit product matrix is reduced to a two row matrix where sum of the row equals the sum of bit products and the two resulting rows were summed with a fast adder to produce the final product. Three bit signals are passed to a one bit full adder ("3W") which is called a three input Wallace tree circuit, and the output signal (sum signal) is supplied to the next stage full adder of the same bit, and the carry output signal thereof is passed to the next stage full adder of the same no of bit, and the carry output signal thereof is supplied to the next stage of the full adder located at a one bit higher position. A Wallace tree is a tree of carry-save adders. A carry save adder consists

of full adders like the more familiar ripple adders, but the carry output from each bit is brought out to form second result vector rather than being wired to the next most significant bit. The carry vector is 'saved' to be combined with the sum later. In the Wallace tree method, the circuit layout is not easy although the speed of the operation is high since the circuit is quite irregularities. (Mano, 1993).

Dadda Multiplier

The array multiplier has more power consumption and propagation delay than the other multipliers. Wallace multiplier has a large-area wastage problem owing to the irregularity in the structure. Vedic multiplier system becomes complex for complex numbers. To overcome these disadvantages of existing multipliers, the Dadda multiplier is proposed. The Dadda multiplier is a fast parallel multiplier that was presented by Dadda in 1965. It is a refinement of Wallace multiplier so the algorithm also has three general stages. The procedure of the three stages is the same for the Dadda multiplier as for the Wallace multiplier. However, in the Dadda multiplier, row reduction is processed by placing adders at the maximum heights of the matrix in an optimal manner. Thus it requires fewer adders than the Wallace multiplier and the reduction process is controlled by the d_j value. where d_j denotes the maximum height of the sequence, $d_j=2$, and $d_{j+1}=\text{floor}(1.5d_j)$. The sequence is $d_1=2$, $d_2=3$, $d_3=4$, $d_4=6$, $d_5=9$, $d_6=13$. The initial value of d_j was chosen as the largest value such that $d_j \leq \min(m, n)$. where m and n are the input bits in the input multipliers and, respectively. If height of $C_i \leq d_j$ then that column does not require reduction and move to the next column. If height of $C_i = d_j + 1$ add top two elements in a half adder, place the result at the bottom of the column, carry at the top of column C_{i+1} , and then move to column C_{i+1} . Else add top three elements in a full adder, place the result at the bottom of the column and carry it at the top of the column C_{i+1} , and restart C_i at step 1. The number of full and half adders needed for Dadda multiplier depends on the size of the operands, as determined by the following equation (Vamsi, 2021): Number of Full adders required = $3 \times$ Number of half adders required = $3 \times$ Thus, the Dadda multiplier requires fewer adders than all other multipliers. Hence area of multiplier is reduced. The power dissipation is reduced and speed is also reduced, because of reduction of partial products which is necessary at each level.

Simulation Results

The simulation was performed using Xilinx ISE 14.7 the results were obtained by writing Verilog code along with its test bench. Using Xilinx ISE software, each multiplier is simulated to analyze its behavior under typical computational conditions. The Array Multiplier, while simple, often results in higher power consumption and area, owing to the extensive use of full adders. The Booth Multiplier, though more efficient in terms of hardware resources, requires additional logic for encoding, potentially impacting the delays. The Wallace Tree Multiplier, which reduces the number of partial products, shows significant improvements in delay, yet its complexity can lead to increased power dissipation. The Dadda Multiplier, optimizing the Wallace Tree approach, offers a further reduction in the area and delay. However, power dissipation remains a critical concern. This study provides a detailed comparison, offering valuable insights into the trade-offs between these architectures for high-performance digital designs, especially in systems where low power, high speed, and minimal areas are paramount. The comparative analysis is done based on the obtained results.

Figure 4. Block Diagram and Internal Structure of Wallace Tree Multiplier

Figure 5. Simulation Waveform of Wallace Tree Multiplier

Figure 6. Block Diagram and Simulation Waveform of Dada Multiplier

Figure 7. Internal Structure of Dada Multiplier

Figure 8. Radar Chart Comparing Various Multipliers

This set of radar (or spider) charts comparing different types of multipliers based on four parameters: Speed, Power, Area, and Complexity. Each multiplier type has its chart, and the orange-shaded area represents the respective multiplier's performance across these parameters. Here's a breakdown of each chart:

Array Multiplier

1. The radar chart shows a balanced performance across all four parameters.
2. It seems to have moderate values in Speed, Power, Area, and Complexity, suggesting a trade-off between these factors.

Booth Multiplier

1. The chart has a sharp peak for Speed, while the other parameters (Power, Area, and Complexity) are minimal.
2. This indicates that the Booth multiplier is optimized for Speed but performs poorly in other aspects.

Wallace Multiplier:

1. This chart shows a strong emphasis on Complexity, while the other parameters (Speed, Power, and Area) are nearly negligible.
2. This implies that the Wallace multiplier prioritizes low complexity but may sacrifice performance in other metrics.

Dadda Multiplier

1. Similar to the Wallace multiplier, the Dadda multiplier emphasizes Complexity, but its radar plot is slightly different, indicating some nuanced performance variation compared to Wallace.

Feature/Multiplier	Array Multiplier	Booth Multiplier	Wallace Tree Multiplier	Dadda Multiplier
Area	High due to regular structure	Moderate, uses encoding to reduce partial products	High, complex wiring for parallelism	Lower than Wallace, optimized reduction tree
Speed	Moderate, operates sequentially	Faster than Array, reduces operations	High, due to parallel reduction stages	Very high, optimized for fewer logic levels
Power Consumption	High, proportional to area and switching activity	Moderate, fewer switching activities than Array	Higher, due to extensive parallelism	Lower than Wallace, fewer active gates
Complexity	Low, straightforward implementation	Moderate, requires additional encoding logic	High, requires extensive parallel connections	Moderate, reduced complexity compared to Wallace
Suitability	Best for simple and small-scale designs	Good for signed number operations and moderate speed	Ideal for high-speed applications where power is available	Best for high-speed, low-power applications

Figure 9. Comparing Various Multipliers

Figure 10. Pie Chart Comparing Various Multipliers

5. Area Distribution: Shows the proportion of physical area occupied by each multiplier type.
6. Power Distribution: Indicates the share of power consumption among the multipliers.
7. Delay Distribution: Illustrates the relative contribution of each multiplier to total delay.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis of various multipliers — Array Multiplier, Booth Multiplier, Wallace Tree Multiplier, and Dadda Multiplier — highlights the trade-offs between area, speed, power consumption, and complexity.

From the comparative analysis table, it is observed that the Array Multiplier exhibits simplicity and ease of implementation but suffers from high area and power consumption due to its sequential operation. The Booth Multiplier reduces the number of operations by encoding techniques, resulting in moderate area and improved speed over the Array Multiplier. However, the additional encoding logic increases its complexity.

The Wallace Tree Multiplier excels in high-speed applications due to its parallel reduction stages, which minimize the delay. Nevertheless, this comes at the cost of increased area and power consumption. The Dadda Multiplier, while similar to the Wallace Tree, optimizes the reduction process, achieving lower area and power consumption with very high speed, making it more efficient for performance-driven applications. The radar chart visually compares these multipliers across the metrics of speed, power, area, and complexity, providing a clear understanding of each architecture's strengths and weaknesses. Additionally, the pie chart illustrates the distribution of area, power, and delay among the multipliers, aiding in selecting the optimal architecture based on application-specific requirements.

In conclusion, the choice of multiplier depends heavily on the target application. For high-speed applications, the Wallace and Dadda multipliers stand out, while Booth's algorithm balances speed and complexity effectively. The Array Multiplier, though simple, may only be suitable for small-scale designs where power and area constraints are less critical.

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